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EPIDEMIOLOGY OF COVID-19 VACCINATION

Abstract.

COVID-19 is a highly contagious viral disease that has caused a large-scale pandemic and millions of deaths around the world [1]. Vaccination has become a key tool in the fight against infection, reducing the level of morbidity, hospitalizations and mortality [2]. The article presents modern epidemiological data on the effectiveness of vaccination against COVID-19, analyzes vaccination coverage in different countries, the impact of booster doses, social and behavioral factors of vaccination adoption, the dynamics of herd immunity, the role of global initiatives in ensuring equal access to vaccines, and the importance of epidemiological monitoring for pandemic control [3].

Keywords: *COVID-19, vaccination, epidemiology, vaccine effectiveness, booster doses, herd immunity, immunization coverage.*

Vaccination against COVID-19 has become one of the largest preventive measures in the modern history of medicine. Its implementation began in December 2020 and already during the first year made it possible to avoid millions of deaths around the world [4]. The WHO estimates that vaccination prevented more than 14 million deaths in 2021 alone, demonstrating its unprecedented global impact [5]. However, the epidemiological effectiveness of vaccination depends not only on the availability of drugs, but also on the level of population coverage, population structure, circulation of virus variants and behavioral characteristics of society. In many countries, the level of coverage remained uneven, which created preconditions for outbreaks and the emergence of new mutations of SARS-CoV-2 [6].

In the early months of the pandemic, the focus was on creating safe immunobiological drugs. At the end of 2021, more than 200 candidate vaccines had been developed in the world, among which mRNA vaccines (Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna), vector vaccines (AstraZeneca, Johnson & Johnson) and inactivated (Sinovac, Sinopharm) were the most widely used [7]. Clinical studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of these vaccines in preventing severe COVID-19 and death in more than 90% of cases [8]. However, the emergence of new variants of the virus, such as Delta and Omicron, led to a decrease in the effectiveness of primary vaccination series, which required the introduction of booster doses [9].

The emergence of COVID-19 vaccines is the result of unprecedented international scientific cooperation. Development projects, which typically take decades, were completed in less than a year thanks to preliminary research in virology, genetic engineering, and

mRNA technologies [9,10]. The accelerated development of vaccines became possible due to the parallel conduct of preclinical and clinical phases of trials, as well as financial support from states and pharmaceutical companies. This model of cooperation has created a new standard for rapid response to global infectious threats, while maintaining safety and effectiveness criteria [11].

Epidemiological studies have shown that even partial vaccination coverage reduces the basal reproductive number (R_0) and reduces the rate of spread of infection. In countries where vaccination rates exceeded 70%, there was a significant reduction in hospitalizations and deaths, especially among people over 60 years of age. For example, in the UK, after vaccination of more than 80% of the adult population, mortality from COVID-19 decreased by 7 times, and the rate of hospitalizations decreased by 5 times [11,12]. Similar results were recorded in Israel, where mass immunization reduced the risk of symptomatic disease by 94% [12].

At the same time, inequality in access to vaccines has become a serious epidemiological problem. According to COVAX, in 2022, less than 25% of the population in Africa received at least one dose of the vaccine, while in the EU this figure exceeded 75% [13]. Such unevenness contributed to the preservation of the circulation of the virus and the formation of new strains. In addition, vaccine laziness turned out to be widespread in many countries — a deliberate refusal or delay in vaccination due to mistrust, fear of adverse reactions, or misinformation on social networks [14]. A study conducted in 2023 in Europe showed that more than 30% of respondents who were not vaccinated justified it by a lack of trust in the healthcare system [15].

An important epidemiological aspect is also the effectiveness of booster doses. Data from the CDC (USA) and ECDC (EU) indicate that the administration of the third dose reduces the risk of hospitalization by 3-5 times even during the circulation of the Omicron variant. The effect of the booster appears as early as 7 days after administration, providing an increase in the titer of neutralizing antibodies and the restoration of the cellular immune response [16]. However, immunity gradually decreases, which creates a need for seasonal or adaptation to new variants, similar to annual influenza campaigns [17].

The dynamics of herd immunity has a complex structure. For SARS-CoV-2, the required level of population immunization was initially estimated at 60–70%, but due to the high contagiousness of new variants, this threshold increased to more than 85% [18]. In many countries, it turned out to be difficult to achieve due to social barriers, uneven distribution of vaccines and constant mutations of the virus. Epidemiological modeling shows that without stable vaccination coverage at the level of more than 80%, the pandemic cannot move into the stage of endemic control [19].

The safety of vaccines is also of great epidemiological importance. Although some adverse reactions (thrombosis, myocarditis, anaphylaxis) have attracted media attention, their frequency remains extremely low — less than 0.01% of all doses administered. International pharmacovigilance systems (VAERS, Eudra-Vigilance) show that the benefits of vaccination far outweigh the potential risks. After mass immunization, there was no increase in mortality from non-infectious causes, which confirms the safety of drugs on a population scale [20].

An important area of epidemiological research is the assessment of the duration of immune defense. Modern observations show that 6 months after vaccination, the antibody titer decreases by 3-5 times, but cellular immunity lasts longer and protects against severe disease. This explains the need for periodic booster campaigns, especially for the elderly, immunocompromised patients, and healthcare professionals. It is among these groups that vaccination demonstrates the highest effectiveness in preventing deaths [21].

Against the background of mass vaccination, the epidemiological picture of COVID-19 has changed: the frequency of severe cases and hospitalizations has sharply decreased, while the share of asymptomatic and mild forms has increased. This phenomenon indicates the transition of the infection to a controlled phase, similar to seasonal respiratory viruses. However, complete elimination of SARS-CoV-2 remains unlikely due to the presence of zoonotic reservoirs, high mutation rates, and incomplete vaccination coverage in the world [22].

Despite all the difficulties, vaccination against COVID-19 remains the most effective means of preventing severe infection. It reduced global mortality by more than half, reduced the burden on health systems, and allowed economic activity to gradually resume in most countries. In addition to a direct decrease in the number of cases of severe disease, vaccination has significantly affected the evolutionary direction of SARS-

CoV-2. The mass formation of immunity in the population created selective pressure on the virus, as a result of which new variants became less virulent but more transmissible [23]. This trend is characteristic of the natural adaptation of pathogens due to an increase in the level of immune protection among the population. At the same time, the decrease in the number of hospitalizations and deaths has reduced the burden on health care systems, allowing them to return to routine work and treatment of other pathologies, which is especially important in the post-pandemic period [24].

Further strategies should be based on scientific monitoring, adaptation of vaccines to new strains, and combating misinformation, which remains a powerful epidemiological factor [25].

Conclusions

Epidemiological data show that vaccination against COVID-19 is a determining factor in reducing mortality, hospitalizations and severe complications. Despite the differences in coverage of the population of different countries, the global effect of vaccination is undeniable. Modern challenges — the emergence of new variants of the virus, the decline in immunity over time, and inequality in access to vaccines — require flexible strategies and constant monitoring. Ensuring equitable access to vaccination, maintaining public confidence and systematically updating vaccines remain key areas of epidemiological control of the pandemic.

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